

THE CONSULTATIVE COMMISSION ON UNALIENABLE RIGHTS UNDER THE US SECRETARY OF STATE AND THE GENEVA DECLARATION (2018-2020): WHEN RELIGIOUS FREEDOM IS BALANCED AGAINST SEXUAL AND REPRODUCTIVE RIGHTS, THEN FORGOTTEN

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In 2019, an Advisory Commission was established within the US State Department. It was announced in the context and milieu of the religious freedom international defence. The members who constituted this Commission were for the most part recognized specialists in religious freedom field and/or at the same time religious leaders. However, this Commission had, as its assigned goal, to reframe the definition of what means “unalienable human rights”, by seeking to "*bring them back*" to their origin.

To this first 'anomaly', was added a second one, namely a contradiction in intentions. The declared and laudable intention, repeated several times and somehow detectable in the final report of the Commission, was to denounce the weakness of the human rights meaning, at the international level, their voluntary or biased misinterpretation by States, which in fact did not respect them. However, it became clear by the choice of the members, by the words and comments of some and others, especially the Secretary of State Mike Pompeo, and finally through the critics expressed about this Commission's existence and aims, that the obvious intention of it, was not to reinforce the human rights defence against all revisionist states and their misinterpretation, but to demonstrate the evanescence of sexual, reproductive and gender rights, in the corpus of the universal human rights, and to claim it at the international level.

1. ANNOUNCEMENT AND FIRST REACTIONS

In July 2018, the State Department hosted its first annual Ministerial to Advance Religious Freedom, a gathering of hundreds of state leaders, “to discuss the

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challenges facing religious freedom, identify means to address religious persecution and discrimination worldwide, and promote greater respect and preservation of religious liberty for all". On July, 16-18, 2019, the second Ministerial, hosted by Secretary of State Mike Pompeo, was even bigger and better than the first. These events were widely viewed as a successful effort to encourage world leaders to promote religious freedom and provided opportunities to brainstorm effective ways to do that. But, in-between the first and the second Ministerial, on May 30, 2019, the State Department announced its intention to create a Commission on Unalienable Rights as well.

The announcement was published in the *Federal Register* and stated that the Commission's purpose was to "provide the Secretary of State advice and recommendations concerning international human rights matters" along with "fresh thinking about human rights discourse, where such discourse has departed from our nation's founding principles of natural law and natural rights." On June 12, 2019, several senior members of the Senate Foreign Relations Committee, Senators Bob Menendez (D-N.J.), Patrick Leahy (D-Vt.), Dick Durbin (D-Ill.), Jeanne Shaheen (D-N.H.), and Chris Coons (D-Del.) wrote to Secretary of State Mike Pompeo to "express (their) deep concern with the process and intent behind the Department of State's recently announced Commission on Unalienable Rights...With deep reservations about the Commission, (they) request that (he) not take any further action regarding its membership or proposed operations without first consulting with Congressional oversight and appropriations committees."²

On June 13, 2019, the U.S. House debated an *en bloc* amendment, which included a provision to defund the Commission. On June 18, 2019, the U.S. House voted 231–187 in favor of the *en bloc* amendment. On June 28, 2019, it was reported that Robbie George, co-founder of the National Organization for Marriage, was involved with the planning of the Commission, just before the second Ministerial to Advance Religious Freedom. On July 7, 2019, Secretary of State Mike Pompeo published an op-ed in *The Wall Street Journal* explaining the Commission's intended focus. He said that "universal," "unalienable" rights must be distinguished from "*ad hoc*" rights granted by governments." Modern references to "new categories of rights", per Pompeo, aim at "rewarding interest groups and dividing humanity into subgroups." He warned that "loose talk of 'rights' unmoors us from the principles of liberal democracy." The Commission was expected to generate debate over philosophical questions such as: "What are our fundamental freedoms? Why do we have them? Who or what grants these rights? How do we know if a claim of human rights is true? What happens

² July 13, 2019. <https://www.foreign.senate.gov/imo/media/doc/06-12-19%20Unalienable%20rights%20commission%20letter%20signed.pdf>.

when rights conflict? Should certain categories of rights be inextricably 'linked' to other rights?". "Today the language of human rights has become the common vernacular for discussions of human freedom and dignity all around the world ... but words like 'rights' can be used for good or evil," Pompeo said: "We must therefore be vigilant that human rights discourse be not corrupted or hijacked or used for dubious or malignant purpose."

The Commission's creation was announced on July 8, 2019. Its purpose was to "advice on human rights grounded in (the American) nation's founding principles and the principles of the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights"³. So expressed, the purpose was to "return" to the supposed American founding principles for enlightening again the international universal rights, in a virtuous process where the US are the best interpreters of human rights.

The following day, State Department spokesperson, Morgan Ortugas, gave a press briefing in which she explained that "authoritarian regimes [are] subverting this human rights context" and claimed that the U.N. Human Rights Commission had become "a laughingstock", what was not completely false... She added that the new Commission would not be "partisan" and did not intend to "create new policy on human rights." But was it the case?

As initially announced on July 8, 2019, the Commission had 12 members, including eight men and four women, as a panel examining human rights through a "natural law lens" according to Mike Pompeo. The panel, which included experts of "varied backgrounds and beliefs," will help, guide American foreign policy commitments by determining what the U.S. considers a human right, particularly when human rights claims seem to be in conflict. The chairperson was Mary Ann Glendon, a former U.S. ambassador to the Vatican under George W. Bush who teaches at Harvard Law School, a very prominent Catholic voice known for her opposition to same-sex marriage and for her efforts to impede abortion as an international human right at the 1995 U.N. Women's conference. The rapporteur was F. Cartwright Weiland, who worked at that time at the State Department. The other members were Peter Berkowitz (Hoover Institution), Russell Berman (Stanford, Hoover Institution), Paolo Carozza (Notre Dame Political Science and Law), Hamza Yusuf Hanson (Zaytuna College), Jacqueline Rivers (Seymour Institut), Rabbi Meir Soloveichik (Congregation Shearith Israel), Katrina Lantos Swett (Lantos Foundation), Christopher Tollefsen (University of South Carolina) and David Tse-Chien Pan (UC Irvine).

³ Laurretta Brown, "Pompeo Launches New 'Commission on Unalienable Rights'", *National Catholic Register*, July 13, 2019.

1.1. RELIGIOUS FREEDOM MILIEU REACTIONS

Several religious freedom bodies, including the Congressional USCIRF, applauded the new Commission, expecting from it ever more improvement of the religious freedom international standards. USCIRF Vice-Chair Gayle Manchin said that “its ability to underscore the importance of religious freedom as a human right will lead to higher impact negotiations on behalf of the more than 70% of the world’s population that is currently suffering persecution or abuse.” She said the new panel would ensure that the protection of religious liberty is “a core element of strategic policy discussions.”

Aaron Rhodes, respected president of the Forum for Religious Freedom-Europe, linked the current disrespect for the religious freedom with a general failure of the human rights understanding and he agreed with the Commission’s purpose. Former executive director of the International Helsinki Federation for Human Rights, Rhodes wrote in the *Wall Street Journal* that “Secretary of State Mike Pompeo deserves praise for proposing an Unalienable Rights Commission to help guide American human-rights policy”. The State Department was accurate in naming natural law and natural rights as “the core foundational principles of human rights”.⁴ Rhodes praised the panel and said that international human rights institutions were infected with “toxic hypocrisy.”⁵ Then he told the National Catholic Register (July 13, 2019) that the Commission was “a response to the politicization of human rights by groups like Amnesty International, whose rhetoric is nothing if not political, resembling Occupy Wall Street-type slogans.” “Human rights obviously have political impact — they liberate people from oppression,” he noted. “But human rights, properly understood, can't be partisan, can't be tied to a political agenda. True human rights are politically neutral; they protect political freedoms, freedoms that can be used to pursue specific partisan objectives. This is not easy for politically agitated people, and for authoritarian rulers, to understand.”

Aaron repeated that international human rights institutions became partisan like the United Nations Human Rights Council, where “many member states have laws that, for example, impose the death penalty for changing one's religion, and which is in fact dominated by authoritarian states that do not believe in universal, individual rights.” Then he pointed out The European Court of Human Rights, “which (was) supposed to defend individual freedom but upholds ‘hate speech’ convictions, for citing facts about Islam,⁶ and upholds bans in wearing Islamic clothing, bans that European countries are embracing”. He said: “Unalienable rights means rights that cannot be taken away by law, but

⁴ Aaron Rhodes, “Pompeo Tries to Rescue the Idea of Human Rights”. *The Wall Street Journal*, June 10, 2019.

⁵ *Ibidem*.

⁶ Simon Cottee, The ECHR's Flawed Ruling on Blasphemy, *The Atlantic*, October 31, 2018.

today human rights are more and more restricted by laws, and international human rights law, which is very weak anyway, is going in the wrong direction. The United States should firmly challenge these tendencies, making sure its own legislation does not make similar mistakes.”

As for the backlash over the State Department’s use of the terms “natural law and natural rights,” Rhodes explained, as an American, the way the Founders likely saw the term. “Our Founders saw liberty as an innate right based on their rational understanding of broad tendencies in nature, that is, on laws of nature that apply to humans, laws that govern our common human nature,” he said. “They observed that human beings flourish in freedom and that despotism corrupts the human spirit.” He argued that “the idea that there is such a thing as ‘human nature,’ however, has become deeply controversial, under the influence of Marxism, Progressivism, Fascism, Postmodernism, and other political ideologies that assert the primacy of social class, or nationality, or other sources of identity, and that can't deal with the fact of individual moral agency and responsibility.” He concluded. “It is sad, and depressing, that the mere invocation of these ideas sets off paranoid and ill-informed reactions by media figures, social activists and ideological intellectuals, but such reactions do not necessarily reflect the society as a whole.”

In the same time, *The Center for Family and Human Rights*, a conservative Catholic think tank, said in an email to its supporters,⁷ affirming that the Commission would “aim an intellectual dagger at the heart of the radical expansion of rights that are not rights, that the hard left promotes at the UN; the ‘right’ to abortion, the ‘right’ to sodomy, the ‘right’ to gender expression.” The Center’s president, Austin Ruse, wrote: “Among the myriad of problems with these new rights, immorality for one, is that these new rights that are not rights have the inevitable tendency to undermine fundamental rights, like the right to religious freedom, the right to speech, and much else”. “We view this new Commission kind of like the cavalry coming to the aid of settlers under siege by savages”.

At the contrary, a letter sent to Pompeo was signed by 125 Catholic theologians and activists – including Miguel Diaz, a former U.S. ambassador to the Vatican under President Obama (2009-2012) and currently a Professor at Loyola University Chicago – called for the immediate abolition of the Commission.⁸ The letter was the result of conversations among Diaz, Dignity USA Executive Director, Marianne Duddy-Burke, feminist theologian Mary E. Hunt, and Fordham University ethicist Father Bryan Massingale. The four

⁷<https://email.opusfidelis.com/t/ViewEmail/j/D06B88B021F872B12540EF23F30FEDED/34A1EB8166AF5B7B46778398EADC2510>.

⁸ "Catholic Leaders Call for State Department Commission to be Dismantled". 22 juillet 2019 *DignityUSA*.

recently participated together in *DignityUSA's 50th anniversary commemoration, focusing on LGBT concerns*. Their public petition expressed concern, among other things, that “the Commission's composition indicated that it was poised to lead to policies that will harm people who are already vulnerable, especially poor women, children, LGBTI people, immigrants, refugees, and those in need of reproductive health services”. The petitioners believe the Commission could violate Catholic concerns: “Our faith and our commitment to the principles of democracy require us to view every person on earth as a full human being. We staunchly support the fundamental human rights of all people and proudly carry on the long tradition in our country of advocating for expanding human rights around the world,” they write. “Our concern is that this Commission will undermine these goals by promoting a vision of humanity that is conditional, limiting, and based on a very narrow religious perspective that is inconsistent with the beliefs and practices of billions in this country and around the world.”

Diaz said in a statement after the letter's release: “The defense of fundamental human rights has been enshrined in our country's most cherished documents. As Catholics we also draw from the recognition and commitment to a broad range of human rights due to all persons expressed in Catholic Social Teaching”. “All human beings have been created in God's image and all have been endowed by their Creator with the fundamental right to Life, Liberty, and the pursuit of Happiness. No person speaking in the name of government or in the name of God can do so to undermine or deny this right,” he said.

Muslim activists have also called on Sheikh Hamza Yusuf, a prominent Sunni scholar who had become a Muslim member of the Commission, to step down and to not collaborate ‘with the most Islamophobic administration in American history’. The debate over Yusuf's role on that Commission among Muslims, seemed focused less on the international human rights implications than on the collaboration with the Trump administration, mirroring perennial debates, over the value of participating in White House iftar events. Yusuf's participation in the Commission was “disappointing and disturbing,” said Shabana Mir, an associate professor of anthropology at the American Islamic College. “His alliance with dictatorial Arab states and monarchs is also disturbing, and this is of a piece with that”, she added.⁹ Several Muslim activists told Religion News Service that they feared Yusuf's social conservatism would colour his foreign policy recommendations on the Commission. Critics pointed

⁹ Yusuf has long drawn criticism for his work advising the Bush administration post-9/11, as well as for his work as vice president of the Forum for Promoting Peace in Muslim Societies, an institution sponsored by the United Arab Emirates. Though Yusuf was once seen as a firebrand imam who railed against Arab autocracies, his involvement in the Forum for Promoting Peace in Muslim Societies has softened his political stances almost beyond recognition. Cf Uzaama Al Azami, “The conflicting legacy of Hamza Yusuf”, TRTWorld, 2019.

to Yusuf's history of dismissing the Black Lives Matter movement¹⁰; his previous comments on homosexuality, which he once called "pathogenic"¹¹, and his comments calling Muslim minority sects disbelievers "outside the fold of Islam."

1.2. HUMAN RIGHTS MILIEU REACTIONS

From their side, some experts in the field of human rights began raising alarms immediately after Pompeo named the members of the commission. Further specifics on the scope of the Commission have not been revealed, although many critics have focused on the language of "*natural law*" and the early involvement of Princeton Professor Robert George, a prominent Catholic defender of traditional marriage, and pro-life advocate. Critics including the *Center for Inquiry* questioned the implications of the Commission's work being framed in terms of "natural law" and religious lens, suggesting that the panel could be used to further a conservative political agenda by denying LGBT rights and reproductive rights worldwide.

Echoing this remark, GLAAD, an LGBTQ rights organization, found that seven members of the Commission had made anti-LGBTQ remarks in the past (9 juillet 2019). The head of the *Council for Global Equality*, an LGBT foreign policy advocacy group, told *The New Yorker* that he worried the State Department planned to create a hierarchy of human rights, with religious freedom sitting at the top¹². Joanne Lin, national director of advocacy and government affairs at the human rights organization *Amnesty International USA*, says that this Commission "appears to be an attempt to further hateful policies aimed at women and LGBTQ people." (July 12, 2019). Roger Pilon, chair of Constitutional Studies for the *Cato Institute*, wrote that, "the distinction between natural law, especially if theologically based, and natural rights to liberty looms large" (July 12, 2019).

On July 30, 2019, a coalition of 220 Human Rights, civil rights, foreign policy and faith organizations leaders and scholars, submitted a letter to Secretary of State Mike Pompeo, urging him once again to dismantle his

¹⁰ Emma Green, "Muslim Americans are United by Trump but Divided by Race", *The Atlantic*, March 11, 2017.

¹¹ Rollo Roming, "When Islam Meets America", *The New Yorker*, May 20, 2013. Cf also Omar Sarwar, "American Muslim Community Must Search Its Soul after Orlando Massacre", *Religious Dispatches*, June 21, 2016.

¹² Masha Gessen, *Mike-pompeos-faith-based-attempt-to-narrowly-redefine-human-rights*, *The New Yorker*, July 10, 2019.

department's new Commission on Unalienable Rights. Organized by *Human Rights First*, the letter's signatories include 21 American religious leaders and dozens of faith-based organizations, as the Presbyterian Church (USA), *American Jewish World Service*, T'ruah, Reconstructing Judaism, the *Anti-Defamation League*, the National Council of Churches, *Muslims for Progressive Values* and *Catholics for Choice*, as well as secularist groups like *American Atheists* and the *Freedom From Religion Foundation*. "(W)e view with great misgiving a body established by the U.S. government aimed expressly at circumscribing rights through an artificial sorting of those that are 'unalienable' and those to be now deemed 'ad hoc' " the letter reads. "These terms simply have no place in human rights discourse."¹³

Senior Vice-President of *Human Rights First*, Ron Berschinski,¹⁴ told in an interview by *Religion News Service*, that, while the commissioners comprised a diverse group of eminent scholars and prominent clergy, their backgrounds largely centred on religious liberty issues and "shared an overwhelming interest in limiting the rights of LGBT people and reproductive rights". Several commissioners' public statements in the past, against contraception and same-sex marriage, and in support of dictatorial regimes "clearly go against the grain" of current human rights discourse, he concluded.

Several months later, in March 2020, some major human rights organizations filed suit over Pompeo's 'unalienable rights' Commission, as the fact that the initiative was an effort to roll back protections for women, LGBTQ groups and minorities¹⁵. *Democracy Forward* filed the lawsuit in the Southern District of New York on behalf of the *Robert F. Kennedy Center for Human Rights*, the *Center for Health and Gender Equity*, the *Council for Global Equality*, and the *Global Justice Center*. They targeted Secretary of State Pompeo, the State Department and the department's director of policy planning staff, Peter Berkowitz. The group alleged that the Commission was created and operated in violation of the Federal Advisory Committee Act, the 1972 statute, that establishes guidelines that such committees must adhere to. In a joint press release, they pointed out that the Commission "stacked with members who have staked out positions hostile to LGBTQ and reproductive rights". It was "holding closed door meetings to conduct significant Commission business outside of the public's view and scrutiny, including efforts to redefine human rights terminology and commitments",

¹³ <https://humanrightsfirst.org/library/coalition-letter-rejects-report-issued-by-state-departments-commission-on-unalienable-rights/>.

¹⁴ Berschinski is currently (since 2021) the Special Assistant to the President Biden, and National Security Council Senior Director for Democracy and Human Rights.

¹⁵ Jennifer Hansler, "Human rights organizations file suit over Pompeo's 'unalienable rights' commission | CNN Politics", CNN, March 6, 2020.

and was “failing to provide adequate notice of meetings and to release key documents to the public.”

In May 2020, 167 rights advocates and organizations from 28 different countries put out a statement expressing "grave concern" about the direction of the Commission and urged it to "reject the prioritization of freedom of religion as a cloak to permit violations of the human rights of women, girls, and lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender (LGBT) people".¹⁶

2. THE REPORT AND THE FOLLOWING GENEVA DECLARATION

Nevertheless, the Commission continued its work. It released a first draft report on July 16, 2020, and one final report on August 26, 2020, arguing for a narrower and more selective approach to human rights¹⁷.

In the first speech releasing the report, Secretary of State Mike Pompeo managed to ignore the report's complexities, and reduce it to Trumpian campaign slogans, about property and religious freedom 's prioritization¹⁸. Moreover, the document's understanding of property rights may be the most contentious, exhibiting a flawed libertarian sensibility.¹⁹ But the report received a lot of good comments.

As The *Center for American Progress* drafted a statement signed by a who of liberal religious leaders expressing "grave concerns" about the report, *The Wall Street Journal* issued an editorial in support²⁰. It was said that the report was fair and historically accurate. It "discusses at length the way the U.S. failed to live up to its founding promise of unalienable rights—most significantly with slavery and the Jim Crow era—and emphasizes that U.S. credibility in promoting human rights abroad depends on America's example at home." The board added that "Mr. Pompeo's initiative (was) not the coded theocratic or authoritarian document of his critics' partisan imaginations", but instead "a sensible effort to put American human-rights diplomacy on more sustainable footing."²¹

Historian of the US foreign policy and founder of a centre-left think tank called *New America*, Walter Russell Mead wrote in the same journal that the report was "a thoughtful and carefully reasoned document that may serve as an

¹⁶ "Groups Express Grave Concern about the Commission on Unalienable Rights". Human Rights Watch. May 1st 2020.

¹⁷ <https://www.state.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Report-of-the-Commission-on-Unalienable-Rights.pdf>.

¹⁸ Pranshu Verma, "Pompeo Says Human Rights Policy Must Prioritize Property Rights and Religion", *New York Times*, July 16, 2020.

¹⁹ None of this accords with Catholic social teaching, which acknowledges a right to private property as a condescension to the effects of original sin and insists that all property has a social mortgage upon it.

²⁰ On July 16, 2020.

²¹ Ibid.

important landmark in future debates". He added that the Commission's approach "offers more opportunity for constructive diplomacy" than approach sought by "many contemporary activists".²²

Michael Sean Winters, a famous editorialist of the *New Catholic Reporter*, a journal considered as left-Catholic, found the report good, in many aspects ²³. There were interesting, compelling issues -he wrote- not least its frequent recognition of how often the Americans do not live up to their founding ideals. For example, when the report discusses Franklin Roosevelt's 1944 State of the Union address, with its articulation of what the President termed "a second Bill of Rights" focused on economic rights such as "the right of every family to a decent home". The report states: "Even as FDR was introducing new rights — or drawing out the latent implications of unalienable ones — the United States continued to deprive African Americans of theirs." The report does seek to clarify some basic philosophic and historical points that might be a tad controversial at the margins but not in essence. For example, it states that "unalienable rights are universal and non-transferable. They are pre-political in the sense that they are not created by persons or society but rather set standards for politics. ... In contrast, positive rights are created by, and can only exist in civil society. Positive rights owe their existence to custom, tradition, and to positive law, which is the law created by human beings. Because custom, tradition, and positive law vary from country to country, so too do positive rights".

It was true, according to Michael Sean Winters, as the report stated, that not "all government forbearance or intervention that benefits some or even all citizens is for that reason a right, and not every right that democratic majorities choose to enact is therefore unalienable." But it was also true that the adage — the rich man and the poor alike are free to forage in the dumpster for their dinner — speaks to the fact that formal rights, if not concretized, invite derision and worse. No one, however, should sneer at the idea of unalienable rights, nor fear defending them and helping them to grow. Winters concluded that, in the long catalogue of human criminality that is history, the emergence of liberal ideas about unalienable rights was "one of the bright spots, and there remains plenty of work to be done to secure and promote those rights".

On the contrary, other comments were less positive. Former U.S. Deputy Assistant Secretary for Senate Affairs under Obama Administration, Rori Kramer, criticized the Commission in an interview with *The Guardian*, saying that "from day one when Pompeo announced this, the intention was always to

²² Walter Russell Mead. "Pompeo Takes on the Politicization of Human Rights" *The Wall Street Journal*, July 16, 2020.

²³ Michael Sean Winters, "Unalienable Rights Are Still Unassailable Despite Pompeo," *NCR*, July 22, 2020.

change the actual working policy of the Department to fit his narrow religious views in a way that really upends the normal working order of the Department”²⁴. In addition, the Commission's report saw opposition from many human rights advocates and scholars. Notable ones include Kenneth Roth, the executive director of *Human Rights Watch*, who described the Commission's report as "a frontal assault on international human rights law." He said that, during a debate On September 17, 2020, organized by the *Human Rights Program of Harvard University* which hosted experts to discuss the report and its implications for U.S. human rights policy and the international human rights system. HRP was joined by Martha Minow, Professor and former Dean of Harvard Law School, Gerald Neuman, J. Sinclair Armstrong, Professor of International, Foreign, and Comparative Law²⁵ and Co-Director of the *Human Rights Program at Harvard Law School*, Mathias Risse, Professor in Human Rights Policy, Global Affairs and Philosophy, Director of the *Carr Center for Human Rights Policy*, Lucius N. Littauer, Professor of Philosophy and Public Administration at Harvard University, Katharine Young, Professor of Law at Boston College Law School. The event was moderated by Sushma Raman, Executive Director of the *Carr Center for Human Rights Policy*, and it was captioned²⁶. This panel was deeply concerned that the report presented a narrower and more selective vision of human rights, calling for rights hierarchies and the dismissal of certain rights as divisive.

Finally, for what extend was this report done? The Commission was dissolved after it, and its conclusions were given to the Secretary of State, head of a department that could use it inside the Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labor or the Bureau of International Religious Freedom, under the supervision of the Under Secretary for Civilian Security, Democracy and Human Rights. It seems that it was not given to them as new guideline. It was not dispatched in the international circle of human rights or religious freedom organizations, as it was previewed for international purposes. Secretary of State Pompeo presented it officially as the new American contribution for the defence of the international human rights at the UN General Assembly in September 2020²⁷. But his sole and apparent intention was to present it as a “prove” in the

²⁴ “US reframing of human rights harms women and LGBT people, advocates say” The Guardian, September 17, 2020.

²⁵ Gerald L. Neuman, Director of the Human Rights Program at Harvard Law School is a former member of the United Nations Human Rights Committee, and had previously submitted formal comments to the Commission outlining its defects: "Gerald Neuman submits comments to State Department's "Commission on Unalienable Rights"". Human Rights @ Harvard Law. March 23, 2020.

²⁶ <https://hrp.law.harvard.edu/events-calendar/watch-pompeos-commission-on-unalienable-rights-shrinking-u-s-human-rights-policy/>

²⁷ Carol Morello, “Pompeo urges other countries to join alternative US views on human rights”, The Washington Post, September 23, 2020.

last move he wanted to manifest, before the American voters, of his devoted “American foreign policy”, in the last days of the Presidential campaign. Having intended to gather friendly countries on the margins of the 2020 World Health Assembly in Geneva, this last move was impeached because of the COVID pandemic. The big Declaration previewed at that time, was finally signed by correspondence on October 22, and the US representative to the United Nations, Kelly Kraft, sent it to the Secretary-General on December 7, 2020, when the world’s attention was occupied by Donald Trump’s denial of his defeat. The *Geneva Consensus Declaration on Promoting Women's Health, and Strengthening the Family*, signed by 34 countries, went unnoticed. The document was not related to the United Nations' Geneva Consensus Foundation or to other Geneva-based institutions and was not legally binding. The signatories declared to have the same main objectives: "(a) to secure meaningful health and development gains for women; (b) to protect life at all stages; (c) to declare the sovereign right of every nation to make its own laws protecting life, absent external pressure; and (d) to defend the family as foundational to any healthy society". Described as "Pompeo's project", the Declaration was submitted by American Ambassador Kelly Craft to the UN General Assembly under agenda item 131 for December 2020. The US position was that there was no "international right to abortion", and that the United Nations should therefore respect national laws and policies on the matter.²⁸ Egyptian NGO Nazra described the declaration as "an international attack on women, gender, and sexuality", and Amnesty International USA said the signatories were "willingly endangering people's health and lives". Critics have accused the signatories of being motivated by the desire to undermine established international institutions. The text didn’t pass into some UN final resolution. On January 28, 2021, US President Joe Biden removed his country from the Geneva Declaration and this declaration is not more available on the website of the US Mission to the UN, but still on the UN website.

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[ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N20/344/30/PDF/N2034430.pdf?OpenElement](https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N20/344/30/PDF/N2034430.pdf?OpenElement):

The signatories “reaffirm that there is no international right to abortion, nor any international obligation on the part of States to finance or facilitate abortion, consistent with the long-standing international consensus that each nation has the sovereign right to implement programs and activities consistent with their laws and policies.”

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